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A Hole in the Black Hole

Open Quantum Collaboration*

March 23, 2024

Abstract

It is widely believed that all matter crossing the event horizon of a black hole is absorbed into its interior. The Planck scale sets a limit on the concentration of matter at the black hole's core. According to general relativity, matter density within the singularity surpasses Planck density, leading us to conjecture that spacetime becomes disrupted. Following black hole formation, matter is theorized to migrate from the core towards the event horizon, driven by a topological force associated with the expansion of spacetime disruptions, culminating in the firewall phenomenon. We heuristically conclude that black holes lack an internal spacetime structure, offering a potential resolution to the black hole information paradox.

keywords: black hole information paradox, singularity, firewall, entropy, topology, quantum gravity

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Introduction

1. Black holes are controversial astronomical objects [1] exhibiting such a strong gravitational field that nothing—not even light—can escape from it [2].

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2. A black hole forms when matter density surpasses the threshold that spacetime can support.
3. It is believed that high-energy quanta, known as the black hole firewall, exist at or near the event horizon [3].
4. At the center of the black hole lies a singularity, which, according to classical general relativity theory, is a point of mathematical infinity.
5. General relativity cannot adequately explain the phenomena occurring within these extreme and colossal quantum objects.
6. However, both theories are robust, and they will guide us in the processes described here.
7. The primary motivation for this work is the area-dependent entropy of a black hole, suggesting that all matter may reside within its surface.

Limits of the Planck Scale

8. The Planck scale provides us with the limits of space and time according to the quantum theories.
9. The Planck density is given by

$$\rho_p = \frac{M_p}{l_p^3} \sim 10^{94} \text{ g/cm}^3,$$

where $M_p = \sqrt{\hbar c/G}$ is the Planck mass, and $l_p = \sqrt{\hbar G/c^3}$ is the Planck length.

10. A typical stellar black hole has a mass of approximately 10^{34} g. If the Planck scale were to be applied within a Euclidean geometric framework, this would imply a volume of approximately 10^6 cm³, leading to an estimated density of 10^{28} g/cm³.
11. If all this mass were concentrated at the minimal Planck length, $l_p \approx 10^{-33}$ cm, the resulting density within the Planck volume of a stellar black hole would be approximately 10^{133} g/cm³, far exceeding the spacetime density limit, known as the Planck density.

12. We conjecture that (11) causes **spacetime** to **tear apart** *inside* the **black hole**, *starting at its singularity*.

13. The line element in terms of the proper time in the Schwarzschild metric is given by:

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right) dt^2 - \frac{dr^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right)} - r^2 d\phi^2. \quad (1)$$

14. In the singularity, where $r = 0$, the ratio $\frac{d\tau}{dt}$ approaches infinity, suggesting that, from the perspective of external observers, time effectively ceases as dt approaches zero.

15. Furthermore, since mass effectively 'slows' time from an external observer's perspective, the maximum mass density could ultimately lead to the cessation of time.

16. Further evidence for our claim is the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy of the black hole [4, 5],

$$S_{bh} = \frac{k_B A}{4l_p^2}, \quad (2)$$

which depends solely on the area of the black hole (A), and not on its 'volume'.

17. k_B is Boltzmann's constant.

18. The **black-hole entropy** is the **maximal entropy** of spacetime [6].

19. The entropy of a black hole, as described in (16), is tied to the microstates (microscopic configurations) of a physical system and is determined solely by the area of its event horizon. This leads to the logical inference that after a black hole forms, all matter is confined within its surface, specifically, the event horizon.

20. The term A/l_p^2 in the entropy S_{bh} represents the total number of *Planck cells* (A/l_p^2) within the surface of the event horizon of the black hole.

The Birth of a Black Hole and the Tear in Spacetime

21. We believe that the following steps take place during the birth of a black hole.
22. We define a *g-hole* as the three-dimensional void formed by the absence of spacetime within a black hole.
23. The symbol *g* represents 'genus' in the context of topology.
24. **Step 1.** The star undergoes maximum compaction, reaching Planck density.
25. **Step 2.** Spacetime tears apart in the singularity.
26. **Step 3.** The mass formerly located in the singularity remains intertwined with space and migrates to the periphery of the *g-hole*.
27. **Step 4.** As new mass arrives at the surface of the *g-hole* and exceeds the Planck density limit, the radius of the *g-hole* expands.
28. **Step 5.** The process continues iteratively until it reaches equilibrium, determined by the event horizon.
29. We are implicitly considering that spacetime possesses finite elasticity.

Discussion

30. The singularity attracts vast amounts of mass and energy, surpassing the maximum capacity that spacetime can support.
31. The result is that the fabric of spacetime tears apart.
32. Matter and energy remain bound to space and time.
33. Particles formerly within the singularity advance towards the boundary of the hole.
34. Once again, the limit is reached; the hole expands, and the process continues iteratively.

35. The process ultimately concludes with all matter and energy residing on the surface of the black hole, leading to the firewall phenomenon [3].
36. One can think of the fabric of spacetime as a rubber band.
37. The fabric will eventually tear apart when the star reaches Planck density, which typically occurs at a radius of approximately 10^{-20} cm for a mass of approximately 10^{34} g.
38. The topological force arising from the puncture in spacetime propels all matter towards the event horizon, akin to a small-scale big bang in reverse, but accelerated.
39. Therefore, based on the premise that spacetime elasticity is finite, we can conclude that there is no spacetime inside black holes.
40. We envision our essay as a foundational step towards a comprehensive understanding of black holes, positing that all existence is confined within the event horizon. This perspective aims to circumvent issues such as the black hole information paradox [7].
41. In this scenario, no information is lost whatsoever.
42. The discovery of black holes radically affected our understanding of general relativity and quantum mechanics.
43. The verification of this conjecture, both mathematical and observational (whether direct or indirect), could shed light on the quantum nature of gravity.
44. Additionally, at a black hole's singularity, spacetime entanglement experiences a 'sudden death' due to intense gravitational forces [8]. This leads to the breakdown of entanglement, causing spacetime to tear apart [9]. Consequently, the void within the black hole expands to reach the event horizon, giving rise to the firewall phenomenon. This process ensures that no information is lost within the black hole.
45. The results proposed here state that *there is no spacetime inside black holes*.

46. There are at least three substantial pieces of evidence supporting this claim: the Bekenstein-Hawking entropy, the firewall phenomenon, and the spacetime information threshold, which refers to the maximum amount of information that spacetime can contain.

The Role of the Singularity

47. The singularity (at $r = 0$) exists only during the black hole formation.
48. After the black hole is formed, there is no singularity since there is no spacetime in its interior.

Experimental Evidence

49. Could the universal interferometric signatures observed in a black hole's photon ring [10] serve as evidence for the firewall phenomenon and the concept of hollow black holes [11]?

Final Remarks

50. In summary, at the very formation of a black hole, spacetime tears apart at its center, causing matter to be propelled towards its outer boundary.
51. This is a topological force by nature, and it is somehow related to topological changes [12].
52. There are a number of topologies that can be defined in a mathematical space.
53. The birth of a black hole implies a change in the original topology of the underlying spacetime.
54. Changing a topology involves modifying the collection of open sets. This, in turn, affects which functions are considered continuous and alters the properties of subsets, determining their compactness or connectedness [13].

55. According to our conjecture, the black hole has the topology of a hollow sphere.
56. We have named the concept described in (55) 'Hollow Black Holes' [11].
57. The transition in spacetime topology that generates a black hole—from the singularity inside to the event horizon outside—aligns with the holographic principle [6, 14]. This principle posits a correspondence of information from a volume to its lower-dimensional boundary.
58. This work lays a foundational investigation and concurs with Stephen Hawking's proposal, which states that 'information is not stored in the interior of the black hole as one might expect, but on its boundary, the event horizon.' This was presented at the KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm [15].
59. Given that all the mass of a black hole is concentrated at the event horizon, the study of black holes will advance to new levels of inquiry, discovery, and understanding.
60. Analogies between black holes and bidimensional materials might shed light on quantum gravity.
61. Some suggestions include searching for topological changes [12] from both applied and pure mathematical perspectives to gain a deeper understanding of this topological mechanism.
62. Other interesting questions arise, such as what the impact of this result is on black hole evaporation.
63. What is the width of the firewall?

Open Invitation

Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [16, 17].

*Join the **Open Quantum Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

The **LaTeX** file for this *white paper*, along with other *supplementary files*, is available in [18, 19].

How to Cite This White Paper

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/js7rf>

<https://zenodo.org/record/10863962>

Acknowledgements

+ **Center for Open Science**

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+ **Open Science Framework**

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+ **OpenAI (GPT-4)**

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [17].

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